

An Experimental Study to Evaluate the Effectiveness of Music Therapy on Quality of Life Among Old Aged in Selected Old Age Home at Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh

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Abstract: The current study aimed to assess the effectiveness of music therapy on quality of life among old aged in selected old age home at Bilaspur Chhattisgarh. True experimental research design is utilized to achieve the stated. **Objectives:** 1. To assess the quality of life among old aged residing at old age home before music therapy. 2. To evaluate the effectiveness of music therapy on quality of life among old aged residing at selected old age home. 3. To associate the post-test level of life among old aged residing at selected old age home with selected demographic variables in the experimental group. **Hypothesis:** (H1)- There will be significant difference in the mean score of quality of life before and after music therapy among old aged. (H2)- There will be significant association between the level of quality of life and selected demographic variables among old aged. **Projected Outcome:** In the present study True experimental research design is used to achieve the stated objectives. The study was based on the conceptual framework of modified Imogene King: Theory of Goal Attainment (1960's). A quantitative research approach is used and pilot study was conducted to confirm the feasibility of the study. For main study purposive sampling was used on 60 samples of old aged residing at old age home. The tool used for data collection consists of sociodemographic variables and modified standardized quality of life assessment rating scale. The data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics where the results show the findings depicted that in the view of inferential statistics there is improvement in the quality of life after music therapy among old aged worked out to compare the difference in quality of life between control group and experimental group. The difference in mean level of quality of life between control group and experimental group was observed 0.43 in control group and 16.24 in experimental group, which was statistically highly significant ($t=0.21$ for control and $t=5.8$ for experimental group) at 0.05 level. Hence H1 is accepted.

Keywords: effectiveness, music therapy, quality of life, old aged of selected old age home.

1. Introduction

Ageing is a natural phenomenon. The process of ageing, a consequence of high birth rate and the increasing life expectancy in the early and middle parts of the twentieth

century, has increased exceptionally at rapid pace. The age criteria to define the old er persons vary across the globe. In India, persons aged 60 years and above are considered older persons. According to a report on world population aging, by United Nations, "the number of older persons was 841 millions in 2013. This is four times higher than the 202 million that lived in 1950. The older population will almost triple by 2050. It is expected to surpass the two billion mark. The proportion of world's population aged 60 years and above increased from 8 per cent in 1950 to 12 per cent in 2013. It will increase more rapidly in the next four decades to reach 21 percent in 2050" By 2050, India will have one sixth the population of older persons in the world. According to a report India had 90 million elderly persons in 2011 and it will grow to 173 million by 2026. Advancing age is well recognized important factor, which contributes to the psychiatric disorders among the geriatric population. The psychosocial variables, like female gender, widows, living alone, unemployed, nuclear family, low education, low social class, physical illness and neurological deficit are significantly associated with psychological disorders in the elderly. The loss of one's job, including voluntary and involuntary retirement, carries with it the loss of financial resources, social status, and much of social network. Some of the challenges, which the aged have to cope with, include retirement, changes in the family structure, new roles, widowhood, grand parenting, illness, loneliness and death in the family. Caring for the aged is part of Indian tradition. The depression in the aged is much less in our country than in the West. In India, elderly persons are held in reverence, are consulted in matters of marriage, festivals, property and they are given prominence in all family functions. The elders also train the youngsters in the family tradition. This has helped elderly people in India in many ways. But in a society that was known for the way in which it cared for its elderly, one is seeing a fast rise in the number of old age homes due to rapid urbanization, nuclear family system and growing economic

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constraints. The elderly people residing in old age homes as a sub-group are rapidly increasing in numbers. They have difficulties much different from the elderly residing in the community. Social issues like being widowed or no one to look after them, make them choose to stay in old age homes. In addition cognitive impairment and physical disabilities also determine the placement of elderly in such homes. The psychological distress in this population could be significant and merits extensive study and research. Very few studies are conducted in India, on people living in old age homes and their psychiatric morbidity. In India, Population ageing, the process by which older individuals come to form a proportionately larger share of the total population, is one of the most distinctive demographic events of the contemporary world. Initially experienced in the more developed countries, the process is now rapidly approaching the developing world. Although not a global phenomenon yet, various predictions indicate that population ageing is going to become a major global issue in the years to come. The need to provide quality mental health care for elders in nursing home settings has been a critical issue, as the aging population grows rapidly and institutional care becomes a necessity for some elders. Music is moral law. It gives soul to the universe, wings to the mind, flight to the imagination, a charm to sadness gaiety and life to everything. It is the essence of order, and leads to all that is good and beautiful. Gerontological consideration explains that music therapy provides comfort to the elderly, music relieves the stress and anxiety. Music therapy minimizes the pain and enhances sleep. Further it soothes and enhances over all wellbeing by adding quality to their life.

The study concluded that music therapy was effective for old aged residing at old age home. Music therapy is considered as a non-pharmacological, safe and side effect free, cost effective, and easy to administer technique.

2. Result and Discussion

Organization of the data: The findings of the study are discussed under following section.

Section-A:

Distribution of sample according to socio demographic variables using frequency and percentage.

Section-B:

1. Analysis of sample according to the quality of life among old aged of selected old age home before and after music therapy.
2. Analysis of effectiveness of music therapy by Mean, Standard deviation and mean difference in the quality of life among old aged of selected old age home before and after music therapy.
3. Comparison of mean difference in pre and post-test score between control and experimental group for quality of life.

Section-C:

Chi square analysis carried out among the old aged of selected old age home to find out the association between post-test level of quality of life with their selected socio demographic variables in experimental group.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of research design

Section-A:

Distribution of sample according to socio demographic variables using frequency and percentage.

In relation to age among old aged of selected old age home the findings revealed that majority of them i.e., 16 (53.33%) from the control group and 11 (36.67%) from the experimental group belonged to age group 60-65 years; 6 (20%) from the control group and 10 (33.33) from the experimental group belonged to age group 66-70 years and 8 (26.67%) from the control group and 9 (30%) from the experimental group belonged to age group above 70 years.

In relation to gender among old aged of selected old age home the findings revealed that majority of them i.e., 30 (100%) belonged to Male for control group and 30 (100%) belonged to Female for the experimental group.

In relation to religion among old aged of selected old age home the findings revealed that majority of them i.e., 21(70%) from control group and 27 (90%) from the experimental group belonged to Hindu, 2 (6.67%) from the control group and 0 from the experimental group belonged to Christian, 4 (13.33%) from the control group and 1 (3.33%) from the experimental group belonged to Muslim and 3 (10%) from the control group and 2 (6.67%) from the experimental group belonged to Other.

In relation to educational status among old aged of selected old age home the findings revealed that majority of them i.e., 15 (50%) from the control group and 26 (86.67%) from the experimental group belonged to illiterate educational status, 13 (43.34%) from the control group and 4 (13.33%) from the experimental group belonged to primary school educational status, 2 (6.66%) from the control group and 0 (0%) from the experimental group belonged to high school educational status, 0 (0%) from both control and experimental group belonged to

degree and post graduate educational status.

In relation to family among old aged of selected old age home the findings revealed that majority of them i.e., 25 (83.33%) from control group and 25 (83.33%) from the experimental group belonged to nuclear family and 5 (16.67%) from the control group and 5 (16.67%) from the experimental group belonged to experimental group.

In relation to marital status among old aged of selected old age home the findings revealed that majority of them i.e., 8 (26.67%) from the control group and 5 (16.67%) from the experimental group were married, 3 (10%) from the control group and 2 (6.67%) from the experimental group were unmarried, 13 (43.33%) from the control group were widower and 19 (63.33%) from the experimental group were widow, 5 (16.67%) from the control group 1 (3.33%) from the experimental group were divorcee and 1 (3.33%) from the control group and 3 (10%) from the experimental group were separated.

In relation to number of children among old aged of selected old age home the findings revealed that majority of them i.e., 11 (36.67%) from the control group and 13 (43.33%) from the experimental group had 1 number of children, 9 (30%) from the control group and 8 (26.67%) from the experimental group had 2 number of children, 7 (23.33%) from the control group and 4 (13.33%) from the experimental group had more than 2 (>2) numbers of children.

In relation to food habits among old aged of selected old age home the findings revealed that majority of them i.e., 21 (70%) from control group and 16 (53.33) from the experimental group were vegetarian and 9 (30%) from control group and 14 (46.67%) from the experimental group were non-vegetarian.

In relation to duration of stay among old aged of selected old age home the findings revealed that majority of them i.e., 16 (53.33%) from the control and experimental group were resident of the selected old age home for less than 5 years and 14 (46.67%) from the control and experimental group were resident of the selected old age for more than 5 years.

Section-B:

The first objective of the study was to assess the quality of life among old aged residing at old age home before music therapy.

Analysis of sample according to the quality of life among old aged of selected old age home before and after music therapy.

The finding revealed that among old aged of selected old age home before music therapy in control group and experimental group in which 3 (10%) belonged to average, 27 (90%) belonged to good and 0 (0%) belonged to excellent criteria in the pre-test in both control and experimental group.

The second objective of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of music therapy on quality of life among old aged residing at selected old age home.

The finding reveals that in control group the pre-test total score of quality of life is 1526, mean is 50.86, mean percentage (%) is 46.24%, SD is 8.32 and post-test total score is 1513, mean is 50.43, mean percentage (%) is 45.84%, SD is 7.48. Mean difference is 0.43 t value is 0.21 P value is 2.05 which is less than 0.05 indicates that there is no significant difference observed in quality of life in control group.

The finding reveals that in experimental group the pre-test total score of quality of life is 1526, mean is 50.86, mean percentage (%) is 46.24%, SD is 8.32 and post-test total score is 2013, mean is 67.1, mean percentage (%) is 61% SD is 12.85. Mean difference is 16.24, t value is 5.8, P value is 2.05 which is more than 0.05 indicates that there is significant difference observed in quality of life in experimental group.

The finding reveals that for control group the mean difference is 0.43, t-value is 0.21 and P-value is 2.05 that is less than the tabulated value at level 0.05 which indicates no significant difference in quality of life in control group. For experimental group the mean difference is 16.24, t-value is 5.8 and P-value is 2.05 that is more than the tabulated value at level 0.05 which indicates significant difference in quality of life in experimental group after music therapy.

The unpaired t-test value was 0.21 in the control group which is less than 2.05 in the tabulated value, but the unpaired t-test value was 5.8 in the experimental group which is greater than 2.05 in the tabulated value that means there is significant difference between pre test and post test score of quality of life in the experimental group that indicates the effectiveness of music therapy on quality of life among old aged of selected old age home. (t-test >0.05, H₁ accepted)

Section-C:

The third objective was to associate the post-test level of quality of life among old aged residing at selected old age home with selected demographic variables in the experimental group.

Chi square analysis carried out among the old aged of selected old age home to find out the association between post-test level of quality of life with their selected socio demographic variables in experimental group.

The analysis reveals statistically that socio demographic variable age, gender, religion, educational status, type of family, marital status, number of children, food habits had no significant association with the post-test quality of life score in experimental group at p<0.05 level.

3. Conclusion

Hence, all the objectives framed by the investigator were achieved and it is concluded that music therapy is effective to improve the quality of life among old aged. As a nurse investigator has to provide information to entire subjects about music therapy and its effectiveness in improving quality of life through non-invasive means.

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